

Energy-Classical Frequency in Quantum Oscillator

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In a previous note (1) we examined the idea of a classical frequency such as that of an oscillator appearing in quantum mechanical results i.e. solutions for the quantum oscillator. In this note, we examine the problem differently. We begin with the quantum oscillator time-independent Schrodinger equation and note that the LHS becomes an equation in the variable y only where $y = \sqrt{km} x$ with $E \rightarrow E/w$. This is already known in the literature, but it suggests E/w must be independent of k and m . For example, if the LHS only has the variable y with no k or m present and y is integrated from $-\infty$ to ∞ , E/w should also have no k , m dependence. At this point, however, w is not really a frequency in the quantum sense. It is a frequency in the classical analysis so one should compare the quantum and classical cases. One may consider the classical conservation of energy equation and integrate over x which may be converted into an integral over t . " w " then allows one to integrate over a cycle, but E/w appears on the RHS as in the quantum case. This seems to show that quantum mechanics picks out special classical energies for which the classical cycle integral produces a value which is not dependent on k or m .

Classical Versus Quantum Energy

The energy of a classical oscillator is $\frac{1}{2}kA^2$ where k is the spring constant and A the amplitude. If one considers any value of A , any value of energy is allowed, but such is not the case in quantum mechanics where one has discrete energy levels. The quantum result is $\hbar w (n + \frac{1}{2})$ where n is the energy level and $w = \sqrt{k/m}$ the classical frequency. In this note we try to investigate why a classical frequency should be present in the quantum energy in such a manner.

Schrodinger Time-Independent Equation

The time-independent Schrodinger equation for an oscillator is:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + \frac{1}{2} k x^2 W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((1))$$

This is a differential equation which does not explicitly make use of classical frequency. For example, in the classical case one has:

$$\frac{1}{2} m \dot{v}^2 + \frac{1}{2} k x^2 = E \quad ((2))$$

This has the appearance of a dot product or a right angle triangle Pythagoras' equation suggesting $\cos(wt)$ and $\sin(wt)$ type solutions which are dependent on classical frequency. Such an approach is not used to solve ((1)), rather one solves a differential equation mathematically without any notion of classical frequency.

It is, however, possible to change variables in ((1)) such that $y = \sqrt{km} x$. One may note that the ground state solution is $C \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x)$ to see this transformation. Thus ((1)) becomes:

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W_1(y) + .5 y y W_1(y) = E/w W_1(y) \quad \text{where } w = \sqrt{k/m} \quad ((3))$$

This suggests that E/w is independent of k , m or $E = w f(n)$ where n is the energy level and f an unknown function. To see this one may note that average energy on the LHS is only a function of y which is integrated from $-\infty$ to ∞ . No k or m appears so no k or m may appear on the RHS. Thus quantum mechanics picks out special energies E such that they are proportional to the classical frequency $\sqrt{k/m}$. Is there any way to consider this scenario in the classical mechanical framework?

The Oscillator in Classical Mechanics

The oscillator solution in classical mechanics is $x = A \sin(\omega t)$ where $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$ and A the amplitude. Consider average potential energy over an oscillation (alternatively average kinetic energy could be considered- the two are equal):

$$\int dx \text{ (cycle) } .5 k x^2 = \frac{AA}{w} \int_0^{2\pi} \sin^2(\omega t) \omega dt \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Integrating } E \text{ over a cycle yields : } E/w \int_0^{2\pi} \omega dt = E/w (2\pi) \quad ((5))$$

Thus E/w also appears in classical mechanics theory, but the difference with quantum mechanics is that any E is allowed i.e. $E = .5kAA$ and A can take on any value (within reason). The link with quantum mechanics is to choose an E such that the integrated kinetic energy over a cycle which equals the average potential energy over a cycle does not distinguish the frequency of the cycle i.e. E/w does not depend on k or m or put another way, the average energy over a cycle is the same for frequencies. This leads to energy being proportional to w .

Loss of Information

In general average kinetic energy (integrated over the x region of a cycle) does not equal average potential energy. In the case of an oscillator, however, it does, so there is a loss in information. In other words, one only needs to know the value of the average kinetic energy. In the quantum case, there seems to be a further loss of information. A quantum solution only picks out certain energy levels and it would at first seem that these have nothing to do with the classical frequency. There, however, seems to be a loss of information such that the integral of E over a cycle i.e.

$$\int E dt = E/w \int_0^{2\pi} \omega dt = E/w 2\pi \quad ((6))$$

should lose all information about k, m i.e. about the classical frequency. Thus all cycles with different classical frequencies are on the same footing in terms of the integral ((6)).

Another way to consider this is to use $E t$ with $t=1/\omega$. This value is constant for ω which is reminiscent of a plane wave with $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. For the free wave there is a special time proportional to $1/E$ and a special length proportional to $1/p$. These two special values keep the action $-Et+px$ (and also each piece $-Et$ and px) constant for all E and p . The quantum oscillator is similar in that t proportional to $1/E$ is also proportional to the physical classical mechanical cycle time of an oscillator. This may be linked to a driver which excites the system. Classically one wishes to have a driver with the same frequency as the oscillator and the same notion seems to apply in quantum mechanics i.e. a photon or phonon with energy $\hbar\omega$ excites the quantum oscillator, but also has the same driving frequency as a classical system. One may note that on average, a quantum system has a v_{rms} which oscillates classically.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum mechanical solution for an oscillator picks out energies E such that the integrated energy over a cycle cannot distinguish the classical frequency i.e. $\int E dt$ is independent of classical frequency i.e. $E/\omega \int_0^{2\pi} dt = E/\omega \cdot 2\pi$. This follows by noting that the time-independent Schrodinger equation may be written in terms of the variable y such that $\psi'' = -k^2 \psi$ with E being replaced by E/ω . Integrating the LHS over y (-infinite to infinite) yields a result which does not depend on k or m so the RHS must also be independent of k, m thus E/ω is independent of k, m and E is proportional to ω . A similar form may be obtained classically by considering average energy over a cycle which is also $E/\omega \cdot 2\pi$. In the classical case, however, any E is allowed, thus it is quantum mechanics which selects special E values which depend on the classical frequency ω linearly such that an integral over a cycle is classical frequency independent.

Reference

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Influence of Classical Frequencies on Quantum Mechanics? (Revised) (preprint, zenodo, 2019)